
AN ASSESSMENT OF FISH POND MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN UVWIE LOCAL
GOVERNMENT AREA OF DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to examine the fish pond management practices in Uvwie Local Government Area of Delta State and was carried out using well structured questionnaire. A total of one hundred and twenty one questionnaires were randomly administer in two major fish farms settlement in the area namely Ekpan and Ugboroke fish farms. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools in the form of frequency unit, percentage and mean. Results of the study revealed that majority (50.4%) of the respondents are females. A high proportion of (44.63%) within age bracket of 31-40 years. Majority were married (71.90%). Majority of the farmers had secondary education (38.02%). Fish farming was not a major occupation (60.33%). The findings indicated that the fish farmers get their water source from the famous Ekpan river, with all having earthen ponds which make production so natural for the fishes. The major constraint therefore includes lack of extension services, theft, lack of good roads and pests and diseases. Rank correlation analysis of 0.5425, shows that there is a high degree of agreement between farmers as regards the constraint of fish farming. Recommendations were given for improving the management practices so that fish production can be increased to meet the increasing level of fish demand in the study area in particular and the State in general.

KEYWORDS: Fish pond management practices, fish farmers, rank correlation, Delta State.

INTRODUCTION

According to Adeniyi (1989), as cited by Maidala and Dantata (2010) noted that fish is an important source of protein in Nigeria which contribute 40-50% of the protein intake of average Nigerians from animal source. Amienghene (2005) reported that fish has a nutrient profile superior to terrestrial meat being an excellent source of high quality animal protein, sulphur and essential amino acid. Supporting this view, Nzeka (2003) asserted that for Nigerians, fish is an affordable source of protein, and the most popular imported species includes croaker, herring, mackerel and catfish. Mackerel fills 65 percent of the domestic market and is preferred by most Nigerians.

Apart from its nutrition effect on man, fish is also a major source of income for many developing countries as well as less developed countries in which Nigeria is not an exception (William et al, 2010). In the same vein, and been more specific, Yunusa and Maidala (2008) noted that other importance of fish include poverty reduction, generating employment and saving foreign exchange by stimulating production at various localities. Fish is also consumed in a variety of forms including fresh, smoked, dried, fried or steamed. (Maidala and Dantata, 2011, citing Oguma et al. 2011).

As the population of Nigeria increases and the supply of fish have reduced due to large scale economic activities which have lead to the pollution of rivers and lakes, thus there is a need to meet this gap by increasing domestic production through fish cultivation.

FAO (2007) reported that globally, consumer demand for fish continues to climb, especially in affluent, developed nation which imported 33 million tones of fish worth over US\$61 billion yearly and some 77 percent of fish consumed globally as food supplied by developing countries.

According to Nwankwo (2005) the fish demand on Nigeria is put about 1.5 million metric tones per annum and the local domestic fish production can only supply 511,700 metric tons; leaning a shortfall of 680,000 metric tons of fish annually. A more recent publication by FAO (2007) put fish supply at 400,000 tons in comparism to 800,000 tons of demand. To meet this local demand, government imports fish worth N50 billion yearly.

Fish farming is believed to be a profitable business based on various literatures on empirical work available, and it is also becoming an area of interest by some individuals who are now becoming aware of its potentials. Corroborating this view, Runfu et al; (2009) reported that fish farming is a profitable venture and its rapidly expanding and it will continue to be profitable if the planning and management are well taken care of.

Based on the foregone presentation there is a need to increase the awareness of fish farming and in doing this the current level of production and pond management practice need to be assessed because as put by Sarka, Chawdhury and Itohora (2006), the expansion of the pond fishing sector is hampered by low level of knowledge of fish farmers on inputs and pond management.

According to Olagunji et al (2007) making references to Spaulding and Blasco (1997) and Assiah (1977) noted that a major constraint to fish farming were identified to be those of environmental impact of aquaculture operation, that is water pollution, inadequate supply of fingerlings, inadequate information and feeds supply. It is on this bases that this study is carried out and to make some suitable recommendation for improving this noble venture. The study therefore seeks to provide answers to the following questions.

- (a) What are the personal and socio-economic characteristics of the fish farmers in the study area?
- (b) What are the types of fish farming practices and characteristics in the study area?
- (c) What are the constraints of fish farming in the study area?

Objective of the study

The main objective of this work was to carry out an assessment of fish pond management practices in Uvwie Local Government Area of Delta State. Specifically, the study intended to:

1. Examine the personal and socio-economic characteristics of the fish farmers on the study area.
2. Identify the pond management practices adopted by the fish farmers in the study area.
3. Identify the production constraint of fish farming business in the study area.
4. Identify if there is any significant relationship between the perceptions of farmers as regarding the problem/constraint encountered.
5. Make recommendations

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis has been formulated for the study.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the rankings of problems associated with involvement in fish farming by farmers from the two farm settlement.

Justification of the Study

The findings of the study will provide necessary and important information to various stakeholders in the fishing industry, these include – potential fish farmers, policy makers, researcher, extension agent and the generality of the problem. Since the study will expose the pond management practice by the farmers, it will help assert government on policy formulation as it affect fish farming, and to the researchers it can be a part of reference material and open areas for the extension agents and all these will lead to increase in fish production with its benefits of increasing the protein intake of Nigerians.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location of the Study

The study area of this research work is Uvwie local government area of Delta State. Effurun is the headquarters of Uvwie Local Government and was established on the 4th of December, 1996. It shares boundary with Warri South Local Government, Okpe Local Government and Udu Local Government. It is a gateway town in and out of the city of Warri; also it is a border town to Osubi Airport in Osubi.

A centre of civilization for the Urhobo people, Effurun is the headquarters of the Uvwie local government of Delta state, Nigeria.

The major occupations of the people residing in the area are farming, trading, marketing ,as well as technician and other highly skilled personnel..

It is densely populated region and has many of the city's finest exotic hotels for relaxation such as Wellington Hotel, Hotel, Excel, Mega Hilton hotel, Casa De Pedro Hotel .

Sampling Technique and Data Collection Method

The survey approach to information gathering was adopted for the study. A multistage random sampling method was adopted for the selection of a total of 121 fish farmers, with whom open and close ended questionnaires were administered. The first stage is the selection of two fish farms settlement on the study area. The second stage is the selection of respondents from the two fish farm settlement using the simple random sampling techniques.

The data were collected from two sources

Primary source and secondary schools. Primary data were collected with the aid of open and close ended questionnaire. The data consisted of socio-economic data, pond management practices, production constraint, etc. and suggestions for improvement. The secondary data include information obtained from publication, textbooks, FAO publications, journal and other materials.

Methods of Data Analysis

The data collected for the study were analysed using descriptive, statistical tool. The descriptive analysis involved the use of frequency counts, distribution, percentages and tabulation of data while Rank Correlation models was used in testing the relationship of the respondents in respect to constraint of fish farming.

$$R_s = 1 - \frac{6(d^2)}{N(N^2 - 1)}$$

Where;

R_s = Rank order correlation co-efficient

d = Difference between two sets of rank (d_1 and d_2)

d_1 = Ranking by fish farmer in Ugboroke fish farms

d_2 = Ranking by fish farmer in Ekpan fish farm

= summation of the difference between two sets of rank (d_1 and d_2)

N = Total number of constraints

d^2 = square of the product difference between two sets of rank (d_1 and d_2)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, the characteristics examined are: gender, age, marital status, educational level, family size, years of fish farming experience, mode of operation, source of funds (capital) and type of labour.

Evidence from the description analysis of the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents as shown in Table 1, indicated that the fish farming business is dominated by female fish farmers (50.41%) as compared to the male fish farmers (49.59%). This indicates the dominance of women in fish farming in the study area. This result corroborates the finding of Ogunyemi *et. al* (2011) but it is at variance with Ogunlade (2007) and Okwu and Acheneje (2011). The age of the respondents was also analysed, the result indicated that those first farmers whose age fell between 31-40 years contributed the majority while on the whole 99.17% fall into the economically active age group of <30 years to 50 years, while the remaining 0.83% accounts for those above 50 years. This finding is in agreement with Lawal and Idege (2004), Ogunlade (2007), Maidala and Dantata (2011) Okwu and Acheneje (2011) who reported that most of the fish farmers are in their economic active years.

Further 72.5% of the respondents were married, while 27.5% were single and 0.83% were widowed. This contributes the finding of Ogunyemi *et. al* (2011) and Okwu and Acheneje (2011). This shows that most of the fish farmers are settled family men and women with responsibilities. According to Okwu and Acheneje (2011), these responsibilities might have propelled them to seek innovation so as to increase their standard of living.

In regards to the educational level of the respondents, 86.78% level above secondary education, thus they as farmers have the ability to read and write which may contribute to their respondent's innovation seeking of new

information. This might be due to the metropolitan nature of the study areas. This finding is in agreement with Ogunlade (2007), Ogunyemi *et. al* (2011) and Okwu and Acheneje (2011).

The family size is an important aspect of most farmers because of the need of labour supply. The result indicated that the fish farmers with family size of 1-5 person dominated the study area representing (52.89%) but this is at variance with Okwu (2011) and in agreement with Ohen and Abang (2009). However, 19.83% of the respondents did not response, this is not a good situation, it goes to show that some person still believe in not disclosing their family size

Table 1: Socio-Economic Variable of Catfish Farmers N=121.

Socio-Economic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	60	49.59
Female	61	50.41
Age		
30	43	35.54
31-40	54	44.63
41-50	23	19.00
Above 50	01	0.83
Marital Status		
Single	33	27.27
Married	87	71.90
Widowed	01	0.83
Educational level		
No formal education	10	8.26
Primary education	04	3.31
Secondary education	46	38.02
Tertiary education	61	50.41
Family size		
1-5	64	52.89
6-10	31	25.62
Above 10	2	1.66
No response	24	19.83
Years of Experience		
1-5	102	84.30
6-10	18	14.87
Above 10	1	0.38
Mode of operation		
Part-time	73	60.33
Full-time	48	39.67
Source of capital		
Personal savings	59	48.76
Family	17	14.05
Cooperative loans	16	13.22
Bank loans	11	9.09
Others	18	14.88
Type of labour		
Farming	61	50.41
Hired	54	46.63
Combined	06	4.96
Extension services		
Yes	33	27.27
No	88	72.73

Source: Field Survey, 2011

Most of the respondents have been involved in fish farming for 1-5 years (84.30%), while 14.87% have been involved in fish farming for 6-10 years white only a small percentage 0.83% have been involved in fish farming above 10years. This corroborates the findings Olagunji et al, 2007, Ogunlade (2007), Ohen and Abang (2009) and Ogunyemi et al 2011. According to Ohen and Abang (2009), this may have been because the fields relatively to new and most persons took some time to understanding it before joining. This agrees with OmotoshoAndFagbenro (2004) that experience matters in adoption of recommended package innovation and modern form techniques. The analysis shows that majority (48.76) of the respondents source their funds for operations through personal-savings while others sources such as family, bank loans, corporative loan and others were 14.05%, 9.09%, 13.22% and 14.88% respectively.

Household labour (family labour) is the dominant type of labour employed by the farmers (50.41%) while the hired labour represent 44.63% and this might be beneficial to the fish farmer since it will reduce cost and income profit but it might not be negliable due to the small size.

Access to extension agents was also analysed the result indicates that majority of the fish farmers had no encounter with extension agent; representing (72.73%) while only 27.27% claimed to encounter extension agent.

Fish Farming Practices and Characteristics by Fish Farmer in the Study Area

This section addresses the second objective of this study that is the pond management practices employed the fish farmers in the study area. Table 2 shows the summary of this fish farming practice employed by the fish farmers. About 100% of the fish farmer’s uses earthen ponds as against 0% for concrete or block ponds.

Table 2: Fish Pond Management Practices by the fish farmer N = 121

Fish Pond Management Practices	Frequency	Percentage
Type of pond		
Earthen pond	121	100
Concrete pound	-	-
Block wall	-	-
No. of ponds (rearing facilities)		
1-5 ponds	100	82.64
6-10 ponds	13	10.74
11-15 ponds	07	5.79
16-20 ponds	01	0.83
Source of fingerlings		
Market	34	28.10
Past harvest	02	1.65
ADP	01	0.83
Other fish farm (hatchery)	84	69.42
Source of water supply for pond		
River/stream	121	100
Borehole/well	-	-
Tap water	-	-
Type of fish stocked		
Catfish	121	100
Tilapia	-	-
Size of ponds (stocking capacity)		
- 500	2	1.65
501-1000	33	27.27
1001-1500	58	47.93
>1500	28	23.14
Type of water treatment		
Lime	121	100
Type of feeds		
Foreign feeds and local feeds	121	100
Land acquisition		
Family	03	2.47
Rent	96	79.34
Purchase	16	13.22
Gift	03	2.47
No response	03	2.47

Source: Field Survey, 2011.

Table 2 shows the pond practices by the respondent. The result indicated the entire fish farmer uses earthen pond representing 100%. This at variance with Maidala and Dantata (2010) but in agreement Okwu and Acheneje (2011). The numbers of pond owned by the fish farmers were also analysed, majority of the respondent (82.64%) had 1-5 ponds, 10.74% had 6-10 ponds, while 5.79% had 11-15 ponds and 0.83% had 16-20ponds. Majority (69.42%) of the respondents obtained their fingerlings from other fish farms which have hatchery facilities .while 28.105 sources from the market. this is in agreement with view Okwu and Acheneje (2011) this result can be explain by .Obande and Solomon (2000) ,they reported that fingerlings source from hatcheries, have high rate of growth and may be free from disease. Also evident from the study shows that 100% of the fish farmers obtain water for their from the Ekpan river they only use borehole for clean up and other activities.

All the respondents (100%) cultured catfish , this might be due to its marketability and preference . this findings is not at variance with the FAOs position (2000) that catfishes have a market value of two to three times that of tilapia. In relation to the pond size, measurement was done base on the number offish the pond can accommodate, since some the fish farmers could not give accurate pond size. Majority of the respondent (47.93%) claim that their ponds can accommodate 1001-1500 fishes; this is closely followed by those that their ponds can accommodate above 1500 fishes.

All the respondent (100%) uses lime in treating their ponds .this view in supported by Okwu and Acheneje (2011) . however Annue and Oniuye (1993) provided explanation for this result, they reported that liming may restore normal water quality, increase benthic production ,clean humid stain and destroy unwanted parasites and other pathogens in water. In respect to the type of feed used, the entire respondent (100%) uses both foreign and local feeds. But not all uses completely foreign feeds because some use the foreign feed at the initial stage of production.

Furthermore, 79.34% of the respondents rented their ponds, 13.22% had their by out right purchase and only 2.47% claim to use family land for their fish farming activities.

Constraints/Problems Failed by Fish Farmers in the Study Area

Objective 3, was to determine the constraints/problems facing the fish farmer in the study area. This is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Constraints/Problem to Fish Production in the Study Area

Constraints/problem	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Remark
Lack of extension services	63	18	4 th
Lack of fingerlings	10	2.86	5 th
Lack of good roads	89	25.43	2 nd
Theft (poaching)	100	28.57	1 st
Pest and Diseases	79	22.57	3 rd
Land acquisition problems	9	2.57	6 th
Total	350*		

Source: Field Survey, 2011.

* = Multiple response

The percentage was based on multiple responses as highlighted in table 3. Theft (poaching) was rank first with a percentage of 28.57 this is closely followed by lack of good roads (25.43%). Third on the ranking table was pest and diseases (22.57%). However lack of extension content was 4th on the ranking scale with a percentage of (18%) while lack of fingerlings come 5th (2.86%) and land acquisition (2.57%).

The issue of lack of good roads was corroborated by Ohen and Abang (2009), this is true because the area of the farm settlement is natural a swamp that was developed. However according to Okwu and Acheneje (2011) the lack of extension agents was relatively high in h is work as one of the major content in fish farming.

Table 5: Rank Correlation Analysis of Constraint to fish farming enterprise as perceived by fish farmers in Ekpan and Ugboroke farms.

Problem	Ugboroke Farm (X1)	Ekpan farm(X2)	Percentage	R _{x1}	Percentage	R _{x2}	d	d ²
Lack of extension services	16	47	26.67	2	16.21	4	-2	4
Lack of fingerling	0	10	0	6	3.45	5	1	1
Lack of good road	7	82	11.67	4	28.28	1	3	9
Theft	26	74	43.33	1	25.52	2	-1	1
Pest	8	71	13.33	3	24.48	3	0	0
Land acquisition	3	6	5.0	5	2.07	6	-1	1
Total	60*	290*	-	-				16

Source: Field Survey, 2011

* Multiple responses

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rank correlation} &= 1 - \frac{6(d^2)}{N(N^2 - 1)} \\
 &= 1 - \frac{6(16)}{6(36 - 1)} \\
 &= 1 - \frac{96}{6(35)} \\
 &= 1 - \frac{96}{210} \\
 &= 1 - 0.457 \\
 &= 0.54285
 \end{aligned}$$

The rank correlation coefficient between the ranking by farmers in Ugboroke and Ekpan farm settlement of constraint in their fish farm enterprises is $r_s = 0.54$. This implies that there is high degree of agreement between farmers from the two farms. Pertaining to constrain ling their inherent in fish farming.

Testing for Significant

H₀: $\rho = 0$

H₁: $\rho \neq 0$

$$\text{Test statistics } t = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

(n - 2) degree of freedom, 0.05 level of significant.

$$\begin{aligned}
 t &= \frac{0.54285\sqrt{6-2}}{\sqrt{1-0.29468}} \\
 &= \frac{0.5428(2)}{0.70532} \\
 &= 1.539
 \end{aligned}$$

Since it is a two tailed test, the theoretical t statistics is $t_{0.025} = 2.776$

Decision: Since $(1.539 < 2.776)$ we accept the H_0 at 0.005 level of significance that means there is no significant difference in the perception of problem of fish farmers from both farm settlements. In other words the fish farmers from both farms have about the same ranking of the fish problem.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The study reveals that the age ranges of 31-40 actively partake on the operation of fish farming. Also the issue of capital shows that majority of the farmer operate from their savings. This implies that they operate on a small scale and cannot reap scale economies. There is also the absence of highly technical know-how by the farmers and no sophisticated or improved technology employed.

However, the absence of extension agents, theft, lack of good road and pest as diseases were major constraint being experienced by the fish farmers in the study areas.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations are hereby made to promote increase fish production in the study area.

- Adequate training and seminars should be held regularly to acquaint the farmers with modern improved technologies.
- Government should reduce the bureaucracy of fund allocation to the fish farmer.
- Farmers should be encouraged to keep record to enable them access their performance and also to provide research data for further researchers.
- Make facilities should be put in place such as storage and processing facilities that will help farmers reduce loss since they do not have storage means but have to set sell doing harvest.

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Received for Publication: 22/04/2012

Accepted for Publication: 12/06/2012

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